

Dielectric Properties of Amides : Molar Polarization, Relaxation Time and Dipole Moment of Amides in Benzene and Dioxane Solutions

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Molar polarization, relaxation time and dipole moment of five amides like Formamide, N-methylacetamide (NMA), N : N-dimethylformamide (DMF), N : N-dimethylacetamide (DMA) and Acetamide have been determined in benzene and dioxane solutions at 25° using the standing wave technique of Roberts and Von Hippel¹ in 3 cm region. The reported results on dipole moment have inferred the existence of a 'trimer' for formamide and a 'dimer' for NMA in benzene as compared to 'monomers' of these amides in dioxane solutions.

A number of communications have appeared²⁻⁸ reporting the dielectric properties of amides to examine the mode of interaction and the role of self-association or intermolecular hydrogen bonding in view of their bio-medical and industrial utility as well as much similarity with water. Although, the subject has received considerable attention through Raman and Infra-red recordings ; but still the findings are limited and scanty in view of the complications involved in solution measurements. Moreover, the data for formamide and DMF have been found to be less conclusive⁷. Thus, from this point of view the present studies are undertaken to illustrate and establish the state of amides as well as to describe their behaviour in solutions from dipole moment measurements.

Experimental

The microwave bench of 3 cm (Type KLB-019 No. 0671, made in India) has been employed for the determination of dielectric constant, ϵ_1 , and dielectric loss, ϵ_2 , by the standing wave technique of Roberts and Von Hippel¹, using the simplified relations of Dakin and Works⁹ as described earlier^{10,11}. These ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 values have been used to calculate the relaxation time, τ , and dipole moment, μ , by Gopal Krishna¹² fixed frequency method for dilute solutions, using the following equations :

$$X = \frac{\epsilon_1(\epsilon_1 + 1) + \epsilon_2^2 - 2}{(\epsilon_1 + 2)^2 + \epsilon_2^2} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$Y = \frac{3\epsilon_2}{(\epsilon_1 + 2)^2 + \epsilon_2^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\tau = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi C} \left(\frac{dY}{dX} \right) \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\mu^2 = \frac{9 kT}{4 \pi N} \frac{M}{d} \left\{ 1 + \left(\frac{dY}{dX} \right)^2 \right\} \left(\frac{dX}{dW} \right) \quad \dots (4)$$

where λ , C, k, N and T represent their usual meaning, d the density of solvent and M and W are the molecular weight and weight fraction of solute respectively.

In order to make an estimate of the precision of equipment, the dipole moments of some of the liquids like, methanol, pyridine and acetone are determined in benzene solution and are given in Table 1 along with their reported values for the sake of comparison. The experimental and literature values are found to be within the maximum deviation of -3%. The obtained lower values of μ are expected to be probably due to the solvent effect^{13,14}.

TABLE 1

Dipole moment (μ) of methanol, pyridine and acetone in benzene solution at 25°

Substance	$\mu \times 10^{18}$ e. s. u.	
	Experimental	Literature ^a
Methanol	1.63	1.68
Pyridine	2.14	2.20
Acetone	2.68	2.76 ^b

^a G. C. Pimental and A. L. McClellan, "The Hydrogen Bond" Reinhold Publishing Co., New York, N. Y. (1960), p. 15.

^b C. P. Smyth, "Dielectric Behaviour and Structure" McGraw Hill Book Co., New York (1955), p. 48.

Formamide and N : N-dimethylformamide supplied by B.D.H. India were treated with freshly ignited quicklime, kept overnight, distilled under reduced pressure and the middle fraction of the distillate collected. The process of purification repeated until the specific conductance of the dis-

tillate reduced to about 10^{-8} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 30°. Whereas N-methylacetamide, N : N-dimethylacetamide and acetamide obtained from E. Merck, Germany; and dioxane and benzene Analar Grade purchased from B. D. H., India were used without further treatment.

Results

The dielectric constant, ϵ_1 , dielectric loss, ϵ_2 , and molar polarizability, P, of formamide, NMA, DMF, DMA and acetamide in benzene and dioxane solutions at different concentrations at 25° are recorded in Tables 2 and 3 respectively. The slopes (dy/dx) and (dx/dw) evaluated from the linear plots of x, y and x, w respectively are used to calculate dipole-moment, μ , and relaxation time, τ , by Gopal Krishna fixed frequency method^{1,2}. The determined values of (dy/dx), (dx/dw), τ and μ are summarised in Table 4.

TABLE 2

Dielectric Constant (ϵ_1), Dielectric Loss (ϵ_2) and Molar Polarizability (P) of amides in Benzene at different concentrations and at 25° ($\lambda = 3.23$ cm.)

Weight fraction (w)	ϵ_1	ϵ_2	$P = \left(\frac{\epsilon_1 - 1}{\epsilon_2 + 2} \right) \frac{M}{d}$ cm ³
<i>Formamide</i>			
0.0208	2.29	0.027	15.0
0.0399	2.35	0.046	15.8
0.0561	2.42	0.059	16.1
0.0746	2.46	0.081	16.7
<i>N-Methylacetamide</i>			
0.0162	2.57	0.161	22.2
0.0313	2.62	0.239	23.3
0.0480	2.66	0.298	23.5
0.0622	2.70	0.349	23.9
<i>N : N-Dimethylformamide</i>			
0.0251	2.68	0.166	20.8
0.0381	2.75	0.306	30.6
0.0595	2.94	0.545	32.5
0.0748	3.00	0.735	34.2
<i>N : N-Dimethylacetamide</i>			
0.0064	2.42	0.058	31.7
0.0196	2.63	0.144	34.8
0.0232	2.70	0.206	35.7
0.0323	2.78	0.223	36.8

TABLE 3

Dielectric Constant (ϵ_1), Dielectric Loss (ϵ_2) and Molar Polarizability (P) of amides in Dioxane at different concentrations and at 25° ($\lambda = 3.23$ cm.)

Weight fraction W	ϵ_1	ϵ_2	$P = \left(\frac{\epsilon_1 - 1}{\epsilon_2 + 2} \right) \frac{M}{d}$ cm ³
<i>Formamide</i>			
0.0075	2.66	0.216	15.5
0.0103	2.69	0.302	15.7
0.0207	2.74	0.528	16.0
0.0314	2.77	0.676	16.2
<i>N-Methylacetamide</i>			
0.0052	2.66	0.243	25.2
0.0096	2.68	0.288	25.4
0.0129	2.69	0.320	25.6
0.0168	2.77	0.406	26.2
<i>N : N-Dimethylformamide</i>			
0.0045	2.59	0.224	24.6
0.0083	2.66	0.270	25.2
0.0153	2.74	0.369	26.0
0.0306	2.88	0.455	27.3
<i>N : N-Dimethylacetamide</i>			
0.0110	2.58	0.200	28.4
0.0202	2.68	0.261	30.3
0.0252	2.75	0.307	31.0
0.0375	2.88	0.424	32.6
<i>Acetamide</i>			
0.0060	2.60	0.167	19.9
0.0101	2.64	0.217	20.2
0.0155	2.74	0.290	20.9
0.0312	2.90	0.443	22.1

TABLE 4

(dy/dx), (dx/dw), τ and μ values of Formamide, NMA, DMF, DMA and Acetamide in Benzene and Dioxane solutions at 25°

Amides	(dy/dx)	(dx/dw)	$\tau \times 10^{12}$ sec.	μ Debye
<i>Benzene</i>				
Formamide	0.24	0.45	4.1	1.11
NMA	1.19	0.41	20.4	2.03
DMF	1.09	1.15	18.7	3.24
DMA	0.37	2.43	6.3	3.03
Acetamide	—	Insoluble	—	—
<i>Dioxane</i>				
Formamide	2.30	1.03	39.4	3.69
NMA	1.64	0.80	28.0	3.17
DMF	0.58	2.50	9.9	3.39
DMA	0.54	2.33	9.2	3.55
Acetamide	0.74	1.70	8.0	2.73

Discussion

It is interesting to observe from Table 4 that the dipole moment of all amides are considerably higher in dioxane to those obtained in benzene solutions. For the hydrogen bonded solvents like, formamide and N-methylacetamide; the μ values 1.11 D and 2.03 D in benzene as compared to 3.69 D and 3.17 D in dioxane are strikingly small i.e., almost 1/3rd for formamide and 2/3rd for NMA concluding the existence of 'trimer' for formamide and 'dimer' (or

better 'dimer equilibrium') for NMA in benzene⁴ to that of 'monomers' in dioxane solutions. This observed anomaly can be reasonably explained in terms of the much stronger dioxane-amide interaction as compared to intermolecular hydrogen bonding in amides : indicating the existence of free molecular dipoles or 'monomers' in dioxane solutions. However, this peculiarity was found to be missing in non-hydrogen bonded solvents like, DMF and DMA on account of the absence of amino hydrogen for bonding to oxygen of neighbouring molecules. The remarkably large decrease for formamide suggests the association at both of the amino hydrogens and the moderate deviation for NMA indicate the intermolecular bonding at amino hydrogen such that the adjacent molecular dipoles are not parallel, but inclined in opposing direction to one another thereby resulting in a net lower dipole moment for trimer and dimer in benzene than for monomers in dioxane in contradiction to the statement advanced by Meighan and Cole^{7,8}. An 'Extended' H bridge model for NMA 'dimer' in benzene has been proposed [supported by spectroscopic evidence¹⁵ as shown in Fig. 1], on the basis of the calculated¹⁴ angle of inclination (142° 40'), using the 'monomers' dipole moment determined in dioxane solution.

Fig. 1. Model of NMA 'dimer' in benzene

Finally, the existence of a 'trimer' for formamide and a 'dimer' for NMA in benzene has been inferred as compared to 'monomers' for all amides in dioxane solutions.

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